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Community center as a Cultural Hub, for cultural heritage conservation

Role of community centers' design in enhancing the quality of life in heritage sites- A case study of "Soor Magra Al Oyoon" district

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Abstract

Community centers are a type of community development services that promote social relationships and mutual support, develop a sense of self-reliance, social responsibility and community cohesion, as well as empowering individuals and families to solve common social problems. In doing so, community centers enhance, one way or another, the community's quality of life. The successful design of community centers ought to accomplish a set of goals in different aspects ;1- Socially, providing a safe place to practice various activities, 2- Environmentally, ensuring a healthy environment through utilizing natural ventilation, lighting, among other passive techniques, 3-Recreational, offering different kinds of entertainment activities, either indoor or outdoor, such as commercial spaces and sports facilities, 4-Economically, attracting different visitors and promoting tourism, 5- Educational, providing a pleasant environment for educational services for the illiterate and children. The importance of the above-mentioned goals is greatly escalated in urban contexts with diverse social, urban and economical status, as in the case of " Soor Magra Al Oyoon" district. A rich historical area that has been severely affected by population growth, deteriorated urban state, plethora of social, economical, and environmental problems. The main aim of the research is to provide an overview of the design criteria of community centers taking into consideration the mutual impacts between the design and the surrounding context, focusing on the significant value of " Soor Magra Al Oyoon" district as one of Cairo's heritage sites, thus ensuring its sustainability.

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Keywords

Community centers; Quality of life; Social impact; Heritage sustainability; Soor Magra Al Oyoon; Management; cosign; public participation; Heritage Conservation; Social; Social Cohesion; Civic Engagement; Social Interaction; Community Hub

1. Introduction

The vision of this project is evident in many different areas, as it provides many services in the care of citizens socially, culturally and leisurely. It deals with all groups of society, both young and old, and where the center prepares the energies of young people to work for the benefit of society and works to increase the social spirit among all the different sectors of society. Its real importance in the consolidation of ancient heritage in the lives of individuals by mixing the heritage of this community with the activities practiced and learned by individuals and become this ancient heritage present and a tool that reflects the culture and urbanization of society.

2. Heritage Conservation

Heritage is a multidimensional idea that is difficult to exactly describe. This is mostly because it is based on cultures' values and clarifications. According to Graham (2002), heritage can be understood in a different way and within cultures at any given time. It can therefore be said that many not the same heritages exist. In addition, the content, clarification, and exemplification of heritage incomes are decided according to current strains. As a result, meanings of heritage differ because its interpretation and personification, are subject to existing societal values and demands. Moreover, as Datel and Dingemans (1988) explain, "principles of historical and architectural importance are shifting constantly" A society's description and care of its heritage are therefore characterized by its value judgments (Jokilehto, 1998).

3. Heritage and identity

The formation of the identity of individuals has a heritage in this region and the design connects the realization of heritage and the preservation of the identity of individuals.

1. Heritage related to Identity.
2. Identity relates to who we think we are and what we want to conserve as heritage in our lives.
3. Identity has close connection to history.

4. Community participation in heritage conservation

The value of the patrimony for society is progressively more underlined. This goes hand in hand with a growing interest in the contribution of local communities in heritage management plans. Although this change in discourse is recognized, its practical implementation often seems too determined and not easy to apply. Therefore, the International Center for Conservation Raymond Lemaire (RLICC, University of Leuven) considered "community participation in the evaluation and management of heritage" as a related and timely theme for its annual international conference, the "Thematic Week" " This volume reports on the conferences and the productive discusses devoted to this theme during the "Thematic Week" of 2014. The conference involved a widespread and holistic approach to community participation. Conventionally concentrating on the conservation of the historic urban environment and the actual parkland, the RLICC seized the opportunity to include intangible and mobile heritage fields, that have a further noticeable connection with the community. (Balén & Vandesande, 2015)

5. Community empowerment as an approach to heritage conservation

The envelopment of community's local people acutely involve in all the activities related to the design and restoration of the conflict resolution through appeals developments and arbitration. At one end of the scale, are community projects that are planned and effected by managers, in which "involvement" refers to the municipal merely providing labor for the projects. At the other end, are projects in which the planning, implementation, management and distribution of benefits are decided by the community, in an expediting policy environment and with the support of project technical personnel and field staff.

In the few projects that some personalities in the community have been involved in, most locals view these projects as targeting certain individuals. Even the community does not know of such a project. In such a case the community views such individuals and the museum with misgiving. Thus, for enablement, government must try to be as transparent as possible to reduce the level of mistrust. Many locals indicated that they have never been involved in any conservation activity because either it is assumed that they know nothing or because they assume the government has enough manpower to handle its preservation demands.

For Empowerment to succeed:

1. Hard work should be made to revive community-based systems of preservation to ensure that societies are in effect partners in conservation.
2. Community facilities to protect sites need to be supported through provisions of tools and other materials that assist in managing.
3. Civic Centers must have a communal outreach officer trained in communal associations and learning.
4. Members of the communal should be involved at all steps right from the time of development design through valuation. (Den, 2014).

6. The Role of Community

1. Heritage should be considered when studying the community
2. Communities and organizations play an important role in determining HCD improving the region.
3. Neutrality, individuals and communities have a personal interest in certain areas and call to designate areas to protect the neighborhood from potential threats and preserve and improve existing buildings and areas. (Balen & Vandesande, 2015)

7. Community involvement in Heritage Management

1. HDC plays an important role in promoting economic revitalization and development
2. Heritage buildings can be used to promote business and attract customers
3. The use of urban heritage for community and cultural development (Santagati, 2017)

8. Community center as a Hub for cultural heritage

A communal center creates social systems and social resources through the activities it provides. The actions are created by all three layers of the municipal center together: The managing layer produces goals for the community center and sets restrictions for what types of activities are allowed, the participant layer creates activities through a group effort and through undertaking while the agree layer maintains the activities that the participant layer creates.

During these activities, social networks are formed. People interact with each other and talk about their lifetime and their problems. Micro-social worlds are produced with their own norms and gives shape to trust. Because of that trust, people feel relaxed in sharing

Figure 1. The Community Center establishes social networks and capital through the activities it provides Soucre Author, data from (Urk, 2008)

Figure 2. Social cohesion; Source Author, data from (Urk, 2008)

9. Community center contribution to social cohesion

Rules are created upon a better considerate of the expectations of citizens (Morrison, 2003). They should take into account the practice the peoples have in neighborhoods. The number of governments in Europe that realize that this is the case is continually increasing (Morrison, 2003). Neighborhoods are pleasant the focal point to match up action from one place to another and to conduct policy involvement upon. The main goal behind this is that a proper social cohesion on the general level can be derived from the quality of the social cohesion at the local level (Morrison, 2003).

The level of social cohesion in the Rivierenwijk is changing and compared to the other neighborhoods it is very low (Deventer, 2014, Nuus & Baks, 2012, Nuus, 2009, Van-der-Velden, 2007). This research can help with uncovering the opportunities and practice the citizens have of their neighborhood. Social cohesion is a concept that is intellectualized by many investigators but most of the time the conceptualization is lacking or self-contradictory to others (Chan, To & Chan, 2006). In the partial debate about the definition of social cohesion many positions have been taken. (Urk, 2008)

Domain	Description
Common values and a civic culture	Common aims and objectives; common moral principles and codes of behaviour; support for political institutions and participation in politics
Social order and social control	Absence of general conflict and threats to the existing order; absence of incivility; effective informal social control; tolerance; respect for difference; intergroup co-operation
Social solidarity and reductions in wealth disparities	Harmonious economic and social development and common standards; redistribution of public finances and of opportunities; equal access to services and welfare benefits; ready acknowledgement of social obligations and willingness to assist others
Social networks and social capital	High degree of social interaction within communities and families; civic engagement and associational activity; easy resolution of collective action problems
Place attachment and identity	Strong attachment to place; intertwining of personal and place identity

Figure 3. The five Domains; shows how they are defined in the article by Forrest and Kearns (2001, p. 2129) Source: Forrest, R., & Kearns, A. (2001). Social capital, Social cohesion, and the community. *Urban Studies*, 38(12), 2125-2143.

10. Role of Heritage Conservation in Achieving Community Improvement

Heritage preservation is a central component of the practice of urban growth, yet designers must often rel on value judgments when influential development strategies (Graham, 2002). Appreciative that new development can occur alongside rebuilding and preservation is indispensable to successfully.

Improvement should reproduce this. As Cohen (1999) states, setting is of chief importance, where the new and standing environment takes preference over the individual. In the process of cultural growth, preserving heritage is important.

By looking at the environmental context, this naturally gives way to continuity. In other words, the urban design should emphasize compatibility with the built-in form and work to "respect standards, height, setbacks, materials and details of surrounding old buildings".

The contrast between old and new architecture may add value to heritage areas and create a sense of local continuity. (Snyder, 2008).

11. Case study

11.1. El Alfarcito

Figure 4. Case study of El Alfarcito, northwesternArgentina, 2013, by Architect: FernandoIbanez Gil flood

11.2. Magra El Oyoum old Egypt

Figure 5. Case study of Magra El Oyoum old Egypt, 2018.

12. Conclusion

As a result of historical reasons, the neighboring community is usually not involved in the conservation and management of heritage sites. Despite some others are involved at nearly each stage of management and is constantly updated on every latest advancement on the site. In certain cases, local communities were confirmed to insist on participating in the actions and management of heritage conservation because they believe that they have their own awareness of preserving the heritage. Though, in many other cases, the local community has been entirely kept out, civic centers are expected to reflect their communities in all aspects of life.

13. Recommendations :

1. Communities should be responsible for a wide range of program opportunities that call to and meet the needs of different youth and should do so from side by side with local entities that can coordinate such work across the entire communal. Individual attention should be positioned on programs for deprived and under-served youth.
2. To increase the probability that a wide range of program chances will be accessible, populations should put in place some locally appropriate contrivance for observing the convenience, accessibility, and value of options for youth in their community life.
3. Private and public funders must deliver the possessions needed at the community level to improve and support community-wide indoctrination that is orderly, coordinated, and assessed in practical methods. Furthermore, supporting at the public level, this is liable to include assistance for transitional authorities and cooperative teams that comprise researchers, funders, practitioners
4. Public and private funders should fund inquiries on whether the features of positive developmental settings predictable in this information are the most important features of communal programs for youth. This research should encourage program design and implementation that meets the different needs of an increasingly heterogeneous populace of youth.

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